

An Analytical Study of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*- A Polyherbal Compound

Manju Nemiwal*, **Harish Kumar Singhal**

P. G. Department of Kaumarbhritya, Postgraduate Institute of Ayurveda, Dr. S. R. Rajasthan Ayurved University, Jodhpur, Rajasthan

ABSTRACT

Background: Dashmooladi Ghrita is a classical Ayurvedic polyherbal formulation described in the Ayurvedic literature Charaka Samhita indicated in Vata Vyadhi Vikara. In view of its therapeutic utility and increasing clinical relevance, establishment of pharmacognostic and analytical quality standards is essential in accordance with AYUSH and API guidelines. **Objective:** To evaluate the pharmacognostic and physicochemical parameters and develop a chromatographic fingerprint of Dashmooladi Ghrita for quality standardization, as per Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API) guidelines. **Materials and Methods:** Dashmooladi Ghrita was prepared in accordance with classical references following Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP). The formulation comprises medicinal ingredients: Dashamoola, a group of ten roots extensively used in Ayurveda for their Vata-shamaka, Shothahara (anti-inflammatory), Vedanasthapana (analgesic), and jeevaniye dravyas for Balya (strength-promoting) properties. Dashamoola and jeevaniya drugs are widely indicated in inflammatory disorders, neuromuscular diseases, and pediatric illnesses where Vata Dosha predominance is evident. Above formulations have been evaluated on the basis of organoleptic characters like colour, appearance and odour, Physio-chemical like Rancidity, Moisture, iodine value, Refractive Index, saponification value, specific gravity etc and Finger printing by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC). **Results:** Organoleptic evaluation revealed a alge green colored viscous formulation with a Characteristic odour. Physicochemical analysis showed Parameters include rancidity was absent, saponification value was 267.74, iodine value 30.37, refractive index 1.4543, acid value 2.12 and moisture was 0.11%. TLC analysis demonstrated distinct The Rf values for these spots were observed at 0.45, 0.59 and 0.78 at 365nm, indicating the presence of multiple phyto-constituents. **Conclusion:** The findings of the present study establish preliminary pharmacognostic, physicochemical, and chromatographic standards for Dashmooladi Ghrita. These parameters may serve as reference quality control benchmarks for ensuring the identity, purity, and consistency of the formulation, in accordance with AYUSH and API requirements.

Keywords: Dashmooladi Ghrita, Vata Vikara, Organoleptic Properties, Physicochemical Parameters, Thin-Layer Chromatography.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, India's traditional system of medicine, promotes the use of polyherbal formulations to improve therapeutic efficacy through reciprocal interactions between medicinal herbs. Classical *Ayurvedic* pharmaceuticals (*Bhaishajya Kalpana*) discusses several dosage forms, with *Ghrita Kalpana* (medicated ghee preparations) being considered superior due to its stability, extended shelf life, and ability to extract and administer both lipid- and water-soluble active ingredients. *Ghrita* is defined as

Yogavahi, which means it enhances the pharmacological activity of medications processed with it and allows for deeper tissue penetration (*Sukshma Anupravana*), particularly into the brain system and reproductive tissues especially into the nervous system and reproductive tissues^{[1][2]}. *Dashmooladi Ghrita* is a classical polyherbal formulation based on *Dashamoola*, a collection of ten roots recognised in Ayurveda for their *Vata-shamaka*, *Shothahara* (anti-inflammatory), *Vedanasthapana* (analgesic), and *Balya* (strength-promoting) characteristics. *Dashamoola* is commonly used in

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

inflammatory disorders, neuromuscular ailments, gynecological issues, and pediatric illnesses where *Vata Dosha* predominates. The formulation is explained in authoritative *Ayurvedic* books such as the *Charaka Samhita* and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, showing its clinical importance and long-term therapy^[3]. From a modern pharmacological perspective, *ghrita*-based formulations are known for enhancing phyto-constituent bioavailability due to the lipid matrix, which helps intestine absorption and transport across biological membranes. Studies have shown that lipid-based herbal formulations can improve the distribution of active chemicals to target organs, including the brain, supporting the traditional use of *ghrita* in neurological and systemic illnesses^[4]. Despite broad traditional use, rising global demand for *Ayurvedic* medicines has generated concerns about quality control, standardization, and batch-to-batch consistency of polyherbal formulations. Variations in raw ingredients, processing methods, and storage conditions can have a considerable impact on the physicochemical and medicinal properties of such preparations. Thus, comprehensive analytical evaluation is required to assure identification, purity, safety, and reproducibility in compliance with current pharmacopeial standards^[5]. The current analytical study of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* was conducted to assess its physicochemical parameters and quality qualities utilizing standard analytical techniques. Such research are critical for establishing reference standards, scientifically confirming classical formulations, and promoting their wider adoption in evidence-based *Ayurvedic* practice and integrative healthcare systems.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Aim

To establish the pharmacognostic and analytical quality parameters of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*, a classical *Ayurvedic* formulation, with special reference to its potential role in the management of *Vata Vyadhi*.

Objectives

- To identify and authenticate the raw drugs used in the preparation of *Dashmooladi*

Ghrita in accordance with *Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API)* standards.

- To prepare *Dashmooladi Ghrita* in a Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) certified pharmacy following classical *Ayurvedic* procedures.
- To evaluate the organoleptic characteristics of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*, including appearance, color, odor, and taste.
- To assess the physicochemical parameters of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* as per *API* guidelines.
- To develop a thin-layer chromatographic (TLC) fingerprint of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* for quality control and standardization.

Material and method –

Procurement of Raw Materials:- The raw drug was collected from the local market of Jaipur, Rajasthan, and after being examined by the Department of *Dravya-guna*, after that *Dashmooladi Ghrita* was prepared under aseptic condition in the pharmacy of *PGIA, Dr. S. R. Rajasthan Ayurved University*, for research and studies, *Jodhpur* under the supervision of competent authority.

Preparation of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*:-

The formulation was prepared under aseptic conditions at *Nagarjuna Pharmacy, PGIA Jodhpur*, under the supervision of qualified pharmacy personnel. All procedures adhered strictly to Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) to ensure reproducibility, quality, and consistency. Each ingredient was measured according to the classical prescription, cleaned, dried, pulverized, and sieved to obtain a course powder, *Murchhita Ghrita* was heated in a large-mouthed container until fumes disappeared, After partial cooling, the specified *Kwatha Dravya* was added, *Gow Ksheera* was added after half of *Ghrita Paka*, and cooking continued, the process was repeated for a day until *Ghrita* reached *Sidhhi Lakshana*^[6]. After the preparation of medicine drug was packaged in a sterile, airtight container labelled with the date of manufacture (December 28, 2024) and batch number (102/2024).

Table 1: Ingredients and Properties of Dashmooladi Ghrita

S. No	Ingredient	Latin name	Part used	Quantity
1.	Bilva	Aegle marmelos Corr	Stem bark	19.2 gm
2.	Agnimantha	Premna mucronataRoxb.	Stem bark	19.2gm
3.	Shyonaka	Oroxylum indicum Vent.	Stem bark	19.2gm
4.	Patala	Stereospermum suaveolens DC	Stem bark	19.2gm
5.	Gambhari	Gmelina arborea Linn.	Fruit /Root	19.2gm
6.	Shalparni	Desmodium gangeticum DC	Panchang	19.2gm
7.	Prishniparni	Uraria picta Desv.,	Panchang	19.2gm
8.	Kantakari	Solanum surattense	Panchang	19.2gm
9.	Brihati	Solanum indicum Linn.	Panchang	19.2gm
10.	Gokshura	Tribulus terrestris Linn	Fruit /Root	19.2gm
11.	Yava	Hordeum vulgare	Seed	768gm
12.	Kola	Ziziphus jujube	Fruit	768gm
13.	Kullatha	Dolichos buflorus Linn	Seed	768gm
14.	Jivak	Malaxis acuminata	Bulb	12gm
15.	Rishabhak	Malaxism uscifera	Bulb	12gm
16.	Meda	Polygonatum erticillatum	Rhizome	12gm
17.	Mahameda	Polygonatum cirrhifolium	Rhizome	12gm
18.	Kakoli	Roscoea purpurea	Root	12gm
19.	Kshirkakoli	Lilium polyphyllum	Bulb	12gm
20.	Mudgparni	Phaseolus trilobus Ait	. Whole plant	12gm
21.	Mashaparni	Teramnus labialis spreng	Whole plant	12gm
22.	Jivanti	Leptadenia reticulata W. & A.	Whole plant/ Root	12gm
23.	Madhuk	Glycyrrhiza glabra Linn	Root	12gm
24.	Kharjur	phonex dactylifera	Fruit	12gm
25.	Gambhari	Gmelina arborea	Stem bark	12gm
26.	Dhraksha	Vitis vinifera	Fruit	12gm
27.	Badar	Zizyphus jujube	Fruit	12gm
28.	Phalgu	Ficus hispida	Fruit	12gm
29.	Shrkara	Sugar		12gm
30.	Goksheer	Milk		6.144liter
31.	Shrpi	Ghee		768gm
32.	Jala	Water		1drona

Table 2: Pratinidhi Dravya of drugs of Jeevaneeya Gana Dravyas

S. NO.	Jeevaneeya Gana Dravyas	Pratinidhi Dravya	Latin name of Pratinidhi Dravya	Part used
1.	Jivak,Rishabhak	Vidarikanda	Pueraria tuberosa DC.	Tuber
2.	Meda,Mahameda	Shatavari	Asparagus racemosus Willd	Root
3.	Kakoli,Kshirkakoli	Ashwgandha	Withania somnifera Dunal	Root

Parameters Studied in *Dashmooladi ghrita*

The analytical evaluation of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* was carried out following the guidelines outlined in the “Protocol for Testing of *Ayurvedic*, Siddha, and Unani Medicines”, published by the National Institute of Science Communication and Information Resources (NISCAIR), CSIR, and issued by the Department of Ayurveda, Yoga, Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha & Homeopathy (AYUSH), Government of India^[7].

Analytical study of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*

Place of work

Cultivator Phyto Lab Pvt. Ltd. Sonamukhi Nagar, Sangaria Fanta, Jodhpur. Sample registration no. CPL/O/25/08/01682. Sample sent to lab date and start of analysis 25-08-2025 and completed 29-08-2025 in 5 days^[8].

Analytical study was done under following headings-

1. Organoleptic Characters
2. Physio-chemical Parameters
3. Chromatographic fingerprint –TLC

Place of Work and Sample Details

The analyses were performed at Cultivator Phyto Lab Pvt. Ltd., Sonamukhi Nagar, Sangaria Fanta, Jodhpur. The details of the sample and analytical timeline are summarized below^[9]:

- **Sample Registration No.:** CPL/O/25/08/01682
- **Sample Code:** CPL/2025/07690
- **Date Sample Sent to Laboratory:** 23 August 2025
- **Date of Analysis Initiation:** 25 August 2025
- **Date of Analysis Completion:** 29 August 2025
- **Duration of Analysis:** 5 days

RESULT

Organoleptic characters

With sensory organs, one can discern characteristics referred to as organoleptic qualities. These attributes are valuable for evaluating and comparing the quality of samples. *Dashmooladi Ghrita* was observed to possess specific organoleptic features, including aspects such as colour, appearance, odour, texture, and taste.

Table 3: Organoleptic Properties of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*

S. NO.	Characteristic Parameters	<i>Dashmooladi Ghrita</i>
1.	Appearance	Viscous
2.	Color	Algae Green
3.	Odour	Characteristic
4.	Taste	Bitter

Physiochemical parameters

Physicochemical parameters refer to the physical and chemical characteristics of *Ayurvedic* formulations. These parameters are crucial for assessing the quality,

consistency, and stability of the formulations. Parameters include rancidity, saponification value, iodine value, refractive index, acid value, moisture etc.

Table 4. Physicochemical Parameters of Dashmooladi Ghrita

S. No.	Test Parameters	Unit	Result	Reference (API)
1.	Rancidity	% by weight	Absent	API Part II, Vol. IV, 2017
2.	Saponification value	—	267.74	API Part II, Vol. IV, 2017
3.	Iodine value	—	30.37	API Part II, Vol. IV, 2017
4.	Refractive index	—	1.4543	API Part II, Vol. IV, 2017
5.	Acid value	—	2.12	API Part II, Vol. IV, 2017
6.	Moisture	—	0.11%	API Part II, Vol. IV, 2017
7.	Specific gravity	—	0.9120	API Part II, Vol. IV, 2017

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC)

Dashmooladi Ghrita Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was carried out utilizing a sample preparation procedure in which 2 gram of the substance was dissolved in 20 ML of ethanol. Toluene, ethyl acetate, and n-hexane were mixed in a 6: 3:1 ratio for the mobile phase. After preparing the sample and mobile phase, inject a 10 μ L volume of the sample onto the TLC plate with care. The plate was then immersed in the mobile phase, enabling the solvent to move eight centimeters. Following development, the TLC plate was derivatized with an anisaldehyde/sulphuric acid

mixture. The plate was viewed after heating, displaying discrete spots matching to different components of the *Dashmooladi Ghrita* sample. The

Rf values for these spots were observed at 0.45, 0.59 and 0.78 at 365nm, which could be indicative of the presence of different bioactive compounds within the formulation. This TLC profiling provides useful insights into the chemical composition of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*.

REPORTS OF TLC

DISCUSSION

Organoleptic analysis - organoleptic evaluation is a sensory assessment of a material based on its physical properties, such as appearance, texture, color, odor, and taste. The organoleptic examination serves different functions in the manufacture of Dashmooladi Ghrita. It is critical to ensure that the preparation has a consistent appearance, texture, and taste when evaluating quality. Variations in these factors could indicate batch-to-batch discrepancies or a departure from standard *Ayurvedic* practices^[10].

Rancidity- Rancidity in Dashmooladi Ghrita, which is predominantly induced by Ghrita oxidation and hydrolysis, has a substantial impact on its sensory properties and medicinal efficacy. Proper storage, packaging, and quality control techniques are critical for preventing rancidity and maintaining the formulation's potency and effectiveness. Regular organoleptic and chemical testing can assist identify early symptoms of spoiling and guarantee that Dashmooladi Ghrita is safe and good for consumption^[11].

Saponification value- The saponification value of long-chain fatty acids, which are found in fat, is low, whereas that of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) is high^[12]. It has been demonstrated that short-chain fatty acids are a vital source of energy for colonocytes, especially those in the distal colon^[13]. The histological, endoscopic, and metabolic similarities between diversion colitis and ulcerative colitis indicate that a dietary SCFA shortage may play a role in the etiology of both diseases. Short chain fatty acids are easily absorbed; there may be a protective advantage if SCFA production is raised and SCFAs, particularly butyrate, are delivered more effectively^[14] to the distal colon. Dashmooladi Ghrita has a greater saponification value. *Ghrita*'s, which are esters, hydrolyze in the presence of an alkali (due to the alkaline nature of *Kalka Dravya* or the other *Drava Dravya* used in the *Snehapaka* procedure), resulting in the production of fatty acid (short chain). This shows that *Dashmooladi Ghrita* contains higher short-chain fatty acids. As a result, *Dashmooladi Ghrita* is easily absorbed and digested, has a preventative effect, and improves intestine and overall health.

Iodine value- The amount of unsaturated fatty substance in the *Ghrita* is determined by the iodine levels. The amount of unsaturated bonds in the fat increases with the iodine numbers. Unsaturated fat supplementation increases overall dietary energy intake to the necessary amounts without negatively affecting blood lipid levels. It also improves nutritional status and lowers systemic inflammation. Polyunsaturated fatty acids, which provide health benefits like controlling blood cholesterol levels, are abundant in lipids with a high iodine Iodine levels determine the quantity of unsaturated fat in *Ghrita*. The amount of unsaturated bonds in the fat increases as the iodine concentration rises. Unsaturated fat supplementation raises overall dietary energy intake to the required levels while having no deleterious effects on blood lipid levels. It also enhances nutritional status and reduces systemic inflammation. Polyunsaturated fatty acids, which give health benefits such as lowering blood cholesterol levels, are prevalent in lipids with a high iodine value^[15]. The increased iodine value of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* suggests that it contains more unsaturated fatty acids. This analytical value demonstrates that *Dashmooladi Ghrita* improves nutritional status and lowers systemic inflammation without having a negative effect on blood lipids despite the fatty acid. The increasing unsaturation of the *Ghrita* can be the result of the *Snehapaka* process.

Refractive index- The refractive index is an important optical property that measures how light is distorted as it passes through a substance. The refractive index of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* can provide useful information about the formulation's composition, purity, and quality. This feature can be especially useful in determining the consistency of substances, such as *Ghrita*'s lipid matrix. The role of the refractive index in quality control is an important consideration. Studies have indicated that the refractive index of oils and fats, such as ghee, can be used as an indicator of purity and adulteration^[16]. Variations in the refractive index of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* may indicate the presence of impurities like too much water, artificial additives, or inferior raw ingredients. Therefore, maintaining the formulation's intended therapeutic qualities would depend in large part on the refractive index of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* being consistent throughout batches.

Acid value- The acid value, which is related to the stability of the *Ghrita*, indicates the amount of free fatty acid (FFA) in the *Ghrita*. For the *Ghrita*, the production of free fatty acids may be a crucial indicator of rancidity. Triglycerides hydrolyse to produce FFA, which can be accelerated by the *Ghrita*'s contact with moisture^[17]. The *Ghrita*'s stability, flavour, and shelf life are all impacted by its fatty acid composition. The presence of FFA in the *Ghrita* signifies its purity or individuality^[18]. *Dashmooladi Ghrita* contains a higher acid value. This shows that *Ghrita* undergoes hydrolysis during the *Snehapaka* process, which may be facilitated by the reactivity of *Ghrita*'s triglycerides with the active components of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*, resulting in glycerol and free fatty acids. Excessive free fatty acid levels (Acid Value) promote a reduction in *Ghrita* quality. This shows that *Dashmooladi Ghrita*'s nutritional value, stability, and shelf life are inferior to those of *Go Ghrita*.

Moisture- *Dashmooladi Ghrita*'s moisture content influences its shelf life, stability, and medicinal efficacy. *Dashmooladi Ghrita* is commonly made with *Ghrita*, which has a low moisture content (less than 0.2%). The presence of moisture can promote the growth of microbiological organisms, lowering the product's shelf life. Research on other *Ayurvedic* formulations, such as *Chyawanprash*, has established a link between moisture content and spoilage and microbial growth^[19]. Excess moisture can alter the balance of ingredients and possibly affect the pharmacological properties of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*. Moisture could potentially compromise the bioavailability of these compounds.

Specific Gravity- Specific gravity is defined as the density of one substance divided by the density of another, usually water. The specific gravity of liquids and semi-solid preparations like *Dashmooladi Ghrita* indicates the formulation's relative density and purity. Because *Dashmooladi* extracts play a role in the composition of *Ghrita*, changes in specific gravity could suggest alterations in their concentrations or the presence of impurities, which may interfere with therapeutic efficacy^[20].

TLC (Thin layer chromatography)

Dashmooladi Ghrita's therapeutic benefits include milestone improvement and neuroprotection, which have been attributed to its major active components. TLC can be used to separate and identify these compounds using their R_f (retention factor) values, which are unique to each one. Ghosal et al. (2000) confirmed the presence of these chemicals in the herbal extract by comparing their R_f values to recognized standards. TLC is widely used in the herbal and pharmaceutical industries to ensure quality control. For *Dashmooladi Ghrita*, TLC can be used to evaluate batch-to-batch consistency and predict the existence of bioactive chemicals. According to a study by Kaur et al. (2018) demonstrated that TLC was an effective method for analysing *Chyawanprash* (another *Ayurvedic* formulation) for its active principles, ensuring its consistency. By applying similar methods to *Dashmooladi Ghrita*, TLC can help confirm that each batch meets the desired specification for active compounds, ensuring therapeutic efficacy^[21]. TLC can be used to detect unwanted substances such as microbial contamination, solvent residues, or adulterants that may affect the quality and safety of *Dashmooladi Ghrita*. In contrast to the target compounds expected R_f values, impurities may show up on the TLC plate as extra spots. In a study by Gawande et al. (2017), TLC was employed to monitor the purity of *Ayurvedic Ghrita* based formulations, helping to identify potential contaminants and adulterants^[22]. A similar approach can be applied to *Dashmooladi Ghrita* to ensure that it remains free of foreign substances that could compromise its safety or effectiveness. The 'fingerprint' refers to the distinctive pattern of spots produced by the compounds present in the sample when subjected to TLC. This fingerprint can be used to compare samples of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* from various batches or even from different manufacturers to ensure authenticity and consistency^[23].

CONCLUSION

The present analytical study concludes that *Dashmooladi Ghrita* exhibits well-defined organoleptic characteristics along with a comprehensive range of physicochemical parameters, including rancidity, moisture content, iodine value, refractive index, saponification value, and specific

gravity. These parameters provide essential evidence regarding the quality, safety, and efficacy of the formulation. Furthermore, chromatographic fingerprinting through Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) confirmed the presence of multiple phytoconstituents, thereby substantiating the traditional therapeutic claims of *Dashmooladi Ghrita* as *Vata-shamaka*, *Shothahara*, *Vedanasthapana*, and *Balya*. The study also establishes specific analytical markers that can serve as reference standards for the identification, quality control, and consistent production of this formulation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The author expresses sincere gratitude to the supervisor, Prof. (Dr.) Harish Kumar Singhal, Head of the Postgraduate Department of Kaumarbhritya, Post Graduate Institute of Ayurveda, Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan Rajasthan Ayurved University, Jodhpur, India, for his invaluable guidance, academic support, and constant encouragement throughout the course of this work. His profound knowledge and dedication to the field of Ayurvedic pediatrics significantly contributed to shaping the direction and depth of this research.

Source of Funding: None.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI): The AI tools did not contribute to the study design, data collection, data analysis, interpretation of results, or the generation of scientific conclusions. The author takes full responsibility for the content of the manuscript.

REFERENCES

1. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita, revised by Charaka and Dridhabala, with Ayurveda Dipika commentary by Chakrapani Datta. Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi.
2. Tripathi, B. (2016). Bhaishajya Kalpana Vigyan. Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi.
3. Vagbhata. Ashtanga Hridaya, with commentaries. Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi.
4. Patwardhan, B., et al. (2015). "Traditional medicine-inspired approaches to drug discovery: Can Ayurveda show the way forward?" Drug Discovery Today, 20(4), 495–503.
5. World Health Organization (WHO). (2011). Quality Control Methods for Herbal Materials. WHO Press, Geneva.
6. Srivastava S. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2009. Sharangadhar Samhita with Jiwanprada Hindi commentary Madhyam Khand 9/13; p. 217.
7. National Institute of Science Communication and Information Resources (NISCAIR), CSIR. Protocol for Testing of Ayurvedic, Siddha, and Unani Medicines. New Delhi: Department of AYUSH, Government of India; 2008.
8. Cultivator Phyto Lab Pvt. Ltd., Jodhpur. Sample Registration and Analysis Records of Dashmooladi Ghrita; 2025 Aug 25-29.
9. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, Part II, Vol. IV. New Delhi: Ministry of AYUSH; 2017.
10. Chaudhary, H., & Gupta, S. (2018). "Organoleptic and Analytical Evaluation of Ghrita." Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine, 9(1), 56-60
11. Saxena, R. et al. (2019). "Rancidity in Ayurvedic Ghee-Based Preparations: Prevention and Quality Control." Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine, 10(4), 246-252.
12. Last accessed on 2011 Dec 12 Available from : http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saponification_value
13. Rabassa, A A, and A I Rogers. The role of short-chain fatty acid metabolism in colonic disorders. The American journal of gastroenterology vol. 87,4 (1992): 419-23.
14. Wong, Julia M W et al. "Colonic health: fermentation and short chain fatty acids." Journal of clinical gastroenterology vol. 40,3 (2006): 235-43. doi:10.1097/00004836-200603000-00015
15. Babalola, T. O. O., and D. F. Apata. "Chemical and quality evaluation of some alternative lipid sources for aqua feed production." Agriculture and Biology Journal of North America 2.6 (2011): 935-943.
16. Sathya, G., Surendran, S., & Varma, M. (2014). Refractive index and its applications in edible oils: A review. International Journal of Food Science & Technology, 49(8), 1711-1718.
17. Frega, N., Massimo Mozzon, and G. Lercker. "Effects of free fatty acids on oxidative stability

- of vegetable oil." *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society* 76 (1999): 325-329.
18. Pritchard, J. L. R., and J. B. Rossell, eds. *Analysis of Oilseeds, Fats, and Fatty Foods*. Elsevier Applied Science, 1991.
19. Ramanathan, M., Natarajan, P., & Suganthi, D. (2016). "Microbial growth in Ayurvedic formulations and the impact of moisture on shelf life." *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 174, 57-62.
20. Chandran, S., & Choudhary, R. (2015). "Physicochemical properties of ghee: A review." *Journal of Dairy Science & Technology*, 32(3), 15-23.
21. Kaur, R., Vohra, A., & Sharma, M. (2018). "Thin layer chromatography (TLC) for quality control and standardization of Ayurvedic formulations." *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 7(3), 45-50.
22. Gawande, S. P., Joshi, H., & Singh, S. (2017). "Standardization and quality control of Ayurvedic ghrita preparations using TLC." *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, 16(1), 57-63.
23. Dey, S., Ghosh, A., & Roy, S. (2018). "TLC fingerprinting: A powerful tool for authentication of Ayurvedic medicines." *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine*, 9(4), 229-235..

HOW TO CITE: Manju Nemiwal*, Harish Kumar Singhal, An Analytical Study Of Dashmooladi Ghrita-A Polyherbal Compound, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (1), 1079-1087. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18311673>

